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Refugee Protection Iraq Country Report

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List of Abbreviations

JCC: Joint Coordination Center

HHRO: Hammurabi Human Rights Organization

IDPs: Internally Displaced Persons.

IOM: International Organization for Migration

MOMD: Ministry of Migration and Displacement

UNHCR: United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

UPR: Universal Periodic Review

WFP: World Food Program

About the Project

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project which aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of 14 partners from 11 source, transit and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden. The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research and to critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and third countries.

RESPOND analyses migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanization. Each thematic field is reflecting a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impacts and responses given by affected actors within.

In order to better focus on these themes, we divided our research question into work packages (WPs). The present report is concerned with the findings related to WP3, which focuses specifically on asylum procedures and refugee protection.

Executive Summary

This report is a study of the conditions of asylum seekers and refugees in Iraq, as well as covering data and scenarios on internally displaced persons, with regard to international protection and other types of protection, and knowledge of the extent of its adaptation to regional and international agreements, instruments and treaties related to the protection of refugees and everything related to human rights and protecting it. In this context, the scope of the report can be summarized as follows:

- The legal, institutional and political framework regarding asylum seekers and refugees in relation to international protection, and it covers the limits of this protection for the period between 2011 and 2017.
- The report presents perceptions, experiences and strategies facing actors at the micro and meso levels, in other words, policy implementers and policy beneficiaries in relation to international protection.
- Policies to implement international protection and its implications, procedures, difficulties and problems, based on the field work carried out by the working group in Iraq through meetings with asylum seekers, refugees and displaced persons.
- The nature of the work and coordination between governmental and non-governmental institutions and other actors that deal with international protection and the extent of their success in assigning work, coordination and cooperation, and the problems arising between these relevant bodies.
- Providing solutions and recommendations within the framework of policies and best practices at the national and local levels.

Therefore, the objectives of this report (WP3) can be summarized as follows:

- Analyzing the international approach for asylum procedures and refugee protection, and the extent of their implementation and impact in Iraq.
- Providing analysis based on analysis of macro-level encounters based on (WP1 national report) and micro-and intermediate (Meso) level analyzes through fieldwork.
- Explaining and evaluating international protection systems at the national and local levels.
- Analyzing the actors at the Meso-level, perceptions, actions and reactions of refugees and displaced persons to asylum procedures and policies and refugee protection.

1. Introduction

The report aims to shed light on the international national protection of Iraq since the international community started to conclude international and regional agreements in this regard. The report also attempts to show the extent of Iraq's commitment to the provisions of laws, customs and international agreements regarding refugees after it became a destination for them, especially in the period between 2011- 2017, as it received more than 250,000 Syrian refugees¹. The number of Turkish refugees of Kurdish origin reaches 11,500, while Iranian refugees reach 8,500, and most of them are of Kurdish origin as well.²

Iraq has yet to legislate a law specific to refugees (humanitarian asylum) (Law No. 51 of 1971 on political asylum does not include provisions that include humanitarian asylum) despite the large numbers of refugees residing in it, especially from Syria, as mentioned above.

The report questions whether Iraq has been able to provide adequate protection for refugees and to what extent was Iraq able to adapt its laws and legislations in accordance with the rules of international law and other international and regional standards, despite its limited experience in welcoming large numbers of refugees within a very short period? The report also seeks to reflect on the national protection in Iraq for internally displaced persons, especially since Iraq witnessed armed conflict in many cities and regions, especially in the years of 2005-2007, as well as exposure to violence and terrorism during the past ten years that affected some cities and escalated in 2014. When terrorist groups took control of large areas of Iraqi territory, the number of displaced people reached more than 3.3 million people in 2014.³

¹ Iraq does not treat Syrians residing in its territory as refugees or asylum seekers, but it considers them guests according to the directives of the National Security Agents Council and the Iraqi Ministry of Immigration to prevent any opportunity to resettle them in Iraq or grant them Iraqi citizenship in the future

² Horizon 2020, Respond, working Papers, Global Migration: Consequences and Responses, June 2018, p.365. www.respondmigration.com

³ Ibid, PP. 369

2. Methodology

The researchers relied on the inductive method in writing this report, where data was collected on international and regional laws, customs, conventions and treaties on the protection of refugees and everything related to it, and to generalize the subject (case) of Iraq on (the situation) in general with regard to laws, agreements, customs and international treaties specific to refugees, that is, the link between the Iraq case study and the international (general) refugee situation. Meaning that they linked the study that they worked on, which is (Iraq) as part of the whole situation. And rely on, in analysis, the information derived from the interviews conducted by the research team at the Micro level with refugees, and (Meso) level with organizations and regional and international agencies, and also on the macro) level with (government entities responsible for managing the displaced and refugees file)).

The comparative approach was used as an adjunct approach in addition to the inductive approach in this study.

The national international protection in Iraq was also identified by collecting information and analyzing data from interviews conducted by the research team with refugees and displaced persons.

The team conducted 29 interviews with the Syrian refugees, 26 of which were with refugees of Kurdish origin representing the majority and 3 from other minorities such as Assyrian Christians or others.

Some 16 of the refugees were male and 13 were female. 17 of them arrived in Iraq between 2011 and 2014, while 12 of them arrived in the period of 2014-2017. They were also distributed in three governorates in the Kurdistan region, 14 in Erbil, 11 in Duhok, and 4 in Sulaimaniyah, and the interviews included 17 refugees from the age group of 18-38 years, (9) among them males and 8 females, while from the age group of 39-59 years, 5 were males and 4 were females, and from the age group between 60 and above included 3 people, (2) of them were male and one female.⁴

As for interviews with internally displaced people, there were 29 interviewees, 14 with males and 15 with females, and 9 represented non-Muslim religious minorities such as Yazidis, Christians, and others. 25 of whom were displaced between 2014-2017 and 4 of them between 2011 and 2014, the interviews also included three age groups (18-38) years, which included (5) interviews with males, (6) with females and ages (39-59) included (6) males and (8) females, and ages (60- and above) included (4), (3) of which were men and one was females.⁵

The field team also held two meetings at the meso level actors and several meetings at the level of decision makers at the macro level.

⁴ Look at table number 2

⁵ Look at table number 3

3. The national system for International Protection

3.1. Brief History of International Protection

Although Iraq has not signed the 1951 Convention relating to the Status of Refugees and its 1967 protocol, it has ratified many international human rights agreements and treaties that refer to refugee rights, including the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966. And the protocol attached to it and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966.

Table 1. The Main United Nations Conventions on Human Rights, to which Iraq acceded

Name of Treaty	Date Joined
International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination	14/1/1970
International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights	25/1/1971
International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights	25/1/1971
Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women	13/8/1986
Convention on the Rights of the Child	15/6/1994
Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the involvement of children in armed conflict	24/6/2008
Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the sale of children, child prostitution and child pornography	24/6/2008
International Convention for the Protection of All Persons from Enforced Disappearance	23/11/2010
Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment	7/7/2011
Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities	20/3/2013

On the regional level, the Council of Foreign Ministers of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation adopted the Cairo Declaration on Human Rights in Islam in Cairo on August 5, 1990. Its articles are essentially in line with the basic principles of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights as well as what was stated in the Refugee Convention of 1951.

In the same context, Iraq has ratified the Arab Charter on Human Rights, which was adopted by the sixteenth Arab Summit hosted by Tunisia on May 23, 2004, which includes articles on refugees and their rights. Paragraph 1 and paragraph 2 of Article 26 of it are as follows:

1- Every person legally present in the territory of a state party to this charter has freedom of movement and choice of residence in any part from that region within the limits of the legislation in force.

2- it is not permissible for any state party to deport any person who does not have its nationality and who is legally present on its territory, except in accordance with a decision issued in accordance with the law, and after enabling him to present his case to the competent authority, unless national security reasons necessitate otherwise, and in all cases, collective expulsion is prohibited.⁶

This came in line with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights issued on December 10, 1948⁷, which Iraq is among the first countries to sign⁸, and also is in line with Iraq's obligations under the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.⁹

Iraq is also a member of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation that issued the Ashgabat Declaration that emerged from the International Ministerial Conference on Refugees in the Islamic World that was held in the city of Ashgabat in the Republic of Turkmenistan on 11-12 May 2012, with the participation of ministers, heads of delegations of member states and the representatives of human rights and international organizations.

The signatories of the declaration expressed their deep concern about the conditions of refugees in the world, especially that most of these refugees are hosted by the member states of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation. They also praised the contribution of the member states of this organization in hosting refugees over their territories. As the 57 member states of this organization host approximately 10.7 million refugees, including five million Palestinians (according to the statistics provided by UNRWA).

And the declaration indicates that the member states continue to fulfill their firm commitment to provide protection to refugees, taking into account their national capabilities and local laws. The declaration also points out that "the 1951 Convention relating to the Status of Refugees and the protocol annexed to it in 1967 represent a continuous value that coincides with the 21st century, and the importance of respecting the principles and values contained in these documents."¹⁰

In this context, on September 20, 2017, the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and the League of Arab States of which Iraq is a member signed a Memorandum of

⁶ The Arab Charter for Human Rights, the most recent version, University of Minnesota, the Library of Human Rights www.hrlibrary.umn.edu, also see, the Arab Charter for Human Rights issued in the series of publications of the National Commission for Human Rights, Doha, Qatar Sunna, p. 11.

⁷ The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, United Nations brochure on the 70th anniversary of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, New York, 2017

⁸ There is no signature

⁹ A brochure in the series of publications of the National Commission for Human Rights, Qatar, Doha

¹⁰ Ashgabat Declaration, 2012 www.alanba.com.kw, published on 5/14/2012.

Understanding with the aim of setting a general framework for cooperation in order to effectively respond to the needs of refugees in the Arab region and facilitate the arrival of humanitarian assistance and humanitarian response in emergency cases.

3.2. The Legal and Political Framework on International Protection

There is no legal text in the Constitution of the Republic of Iraq that refers to organizing the issue of immigration and refugees, except as stated in the second of Article (21), which states:

"The right to political asylum in Iraq is regulated by law and it is not permissible to extradite a political refugee to a foreign entity or forcibly return him to the country from which they fled."

Also, the third paragraph of the same article came with the following text:

"Political asylum is not granted to those accused of international or terrorist crimes, or whoever harms Iraq."¹¹

Other than that, the Iraqi Constitution did not refer to the issue of refugees and immigration to Iraq, and there is a draft law submitted by the permanent committee for refugee affairs linked to the Iraqi Ministry of the Interior since 2016, and the Iraqi cabinet has referred this project to the Iraqi parliament, which in turn has not yet legalized it. However, there is the Political Refugees Law No. 51 of 1971, which regulates the lives of asylum seekers in Iraq.

Iraq also legislated the Residence of Foreigners Law No. (76) of 2017, in which it did not address the issue of immigration and refugees.¹²

The Ministry of Immigration and Displacement Law No.21 of 2009 is one of the laws adopted by Iraq to organize and improve the conditions of internally displaced persons and refugees in Iraq in accordance with the standards and guidelines of the United Nations and the rules of international law that work with Iraqi national interests.

3.3. The institutional framework and actors with regard to international protection

The Iraqi institutions and bodies that take upon themselves the concern and follow-up of refugee and internally displaced cases, and strive to provide protection for them are many. Some are governmental and others are independent bodies in Iraq, and they work in a coordinated and cooperative manner with each other. The governmental institutions that exclusively concerned with refugees are Ministry of interior, represented by the Permanent Committee for Refugees Affairs and the Ministry of Immigration and Displacement, a ministry established after 2003 and whose primary tasks are to take care of the issue of migration, refugees and internally displaced persons. From the regional authorities that deal with refugee and displaced issues is a regional authority of Kurdistan Iraq. At the local level, there are the authorities of on-the-border provinces in particular and other provinces in Iraq in general, and

¹¹ The Constitution of the Republic of Iraq, Fact Sheet / Iraqi Issue No. 2012, 28/12/2015.

¹² www.alsumaria.tv. Publication 12/23/2017

independent national bodies. Like the High Commission for Human Rights, which also does follow up of refugees and displaced persons in the framework of respect and protecting human rights.

On the one hand, there is cooperation and coordination between these institutions through joint committees on issues related to the rights of refugees and internally displaced persons, and on the other hand, they carry out their tasks through coordination with international, regional and local organizations concerned in this field, especially the UNHCR and the International Organization for Migration (IOM), The World Food Program (WFP), the International Red Cross, and Qandil (Swedish Humanitarian Aid Organization), as well as dozens of local, national NGOs provide humanitarian assistance to refugees and displaced people.

It should be noted that these organizations have played an essential role in assisting refugees and asylum seekers, in reducing statelessness and responding to it through a regional response plan to support refugees and empower their host communities. What confirm this role is the coordination that took place between Iraq and the UNHCR in dealing with the situation of Iranian political refugees (Mujahideen Khalq) who had been in Iraq, and were opposed to the current Iranian regime, because their legal status was not clear, after the political changes that occurred in Iraq after 2003. Finally, the issue was resolved by signing an agreement between the UNHCR and Iraq to resettle them in Albania, in September 2016 ¹³

3.4. Definitions and Perceptions of Protection at the National Level

Concepts of International Protection, Key Topics / Stories (Qualitative Content Analysis) - Perceptions of International Protection, Problems, and Solutions

The topic of protection in national law is closely related to the definition of a refugee, and the Political Refugee Law No. (51) of the year 1971, which is currently in effect, does not refer to the types of temporary or permanent protection. Although Iraq has not yet enacted a comprehensive law for refugees, it looks at international protection at the national level within the framework of its existing laws, treaties, agreements, declarations and international instruments that it signed or joined, especially those related to human rights, which have already been mentioned above. As Iraq provides protection within the framework of the Political Refugees Law No. 51 of 1971, as well as the Law of the Ministry of Immigration and Displacement No. (21) of 2009, and the decisions and orders of the Permanent Committee for Refugees, in light of the memorandum of understanding and coordination between the Iraqi government and the UNHCR as well as memorandum of understanding for protection between the Kurdistan Regional Government of Iraq and the Commission itself.

Article 2 of the Law of the Ministry of Displacement and Migration indicates clear definitions of refugees, internally displaced persons and Palestinian refugees. This article specifies that refugees to Iraq of other nationalities are the ones who “resorted to it as a result of being persecuted because of race, religion, nationality, belonging to a certain social group or political opinions, or as a result of exposure to public violence or events that seriously disturb public

¹³ Horizon 2020, Respond, Working Papers, Global Migration: Consequences and Responses, June 2018, p.377, www.respondmigration.com

security or threaten their lives or their physical safety or liberties and those who have taken refuge in accordance with international law and agreements to which Iraq is a party".

While the same article defines IDPs as "Iraqis forced to flee their homes or left their usual place of residence inside Iraq to avoid the effects of armed conflict, general violence, violation of human rights, natural disasters caused by human beings or abuse of authority or due to development projects.". This law also defines Palestinian refugees "who were forced to leave their homeland since 1948 and resided legally in Iraq and were accepted as refugees."¹⁴

Article 3 also stresses the endeavor to improve the conditions of Iraqi IDPs and refugees to Iraq of other nationalities, to reach a minimum as a basis to be determined based on clear and specific criteria in light of the United Nations guidelines and international laws and norms, taking into consideration the national interest and internal considerations. The same article also emphasizes coordination and cooperation with the concerned authorities inside and outside Iraq to provide solutions or provide services. Likewise, the Ministry of Immigration and Displacement coordinates and cooperates with the UNHCR and international and humanitarian organizations in all matters related to refugee affairs, and it also coordinates and cooperates with the permanent committee for refugee affairs in seeking to establish a database with them that includes information on asylum seekers and refugees and their status legally, issuing identification documents to them, and everything that would enhance their protection.

Although Iraq, as mentioned above, has a system of legal rules and appropriate mechanisms in protecting asylum seekers and refugees, in addition to what is imposed by its international human rights obligations, there are many challenges and problems that still stand in the way of achieving an integrated protection system that covers the rights of asylum seekers and refugees.

It is worth noting here that Iraq has a social and religious specificity, it is important to take into account, for example, Iraq will not accept asylum applications due to persecution due to the sexual orientation, and the current refugee bill states it explicitly.¹⁵

Some of these legislative challenges are represented in its inability to pass the refugee bill proposed by the Ministry of Displacement and Migration and the Permanent Committee for Refugees¹⁶ , Others are related to the intellectual structure of the political blocs that lead the political process that warns Iraq for expanding its circle of international obligations, especially

¹⁴ Law of the Ministry of Immigration and Displaced, Article 2, 2009.

¹⁵ Star Nowruz, Director General of the Branches Department at the Ministry of Displacement and Migration, Roundtable Meeting, Baghdad, 12/15/2018

¹⁶ The proposed refugee law: It is the draft refugee law prepared by the relevant authorities in the Ministry of Immigration and Displaced and the Ministry of Interior represented by the Permanent Committee for Refugee Affairs in 2017, for organizing refugee rules and its provisions in Iraq to include all cases of humanitarian and political asylum due to persecution and threats based on race, religion or nationality or social affiliation, in line of the provisions of the Constitution of Iraq, international agreements and the enforcing laws with finding the relevant administrative structure, but this law has not been legislated until now. According to the letter of General Secretariat of the Council of Ministers, office of the Council of Ministers and Committees Affairs No. 041429 on December 28, 2017.

regarding the issue of refugees, and that Iraq remains to this day not signatory of the 1951 Refugee Convention. Therefore, its legal framework is not clear enough to deal with refugee affairs in general. Rather, it deals with each case independently, which creates a distinction between them according to the prevailing political trends in each stage. The legal adaptation of refugees is not controlled in Iraq, and not all refugees are treated according to the same principles.¹⁷

Also, the political and security instability in the country from 2003 to 2017 cast a shadow over the refugee situation and ways of protecting them, which was reflected in the legal status of Palestinian refugees.

The issuance of the Foreigners' Residence Law No. (76) of 2017 revoke the privileges included in the Saddam regime's decisions, which gave Palestinian refugees the rights of the Iraqi citizen to live, to own property, work, jobs, education, etc. As the Revolutionary Command Council had issued during the Saddam regime many decisions to regulate the affairs of Palestinian refugees in Iraq, such as Resolution (131) regarding compulsory education for their children and Resolution (202) that gives Palestinian refugees all the rights of the Iraqi citizen, that canceling this decision has caused a lot of repercussions on the Palestinian families, for example, the food ration was withheld from the Palestinian refugees in June 2018, which led to the deprivation of 106 Palestinian families of them, forcing the Palestinian ambassador in Baghdad to meet the Iraqi Minister of Trade to lift this ban¹⁸, and Likewise, the resolution (366) of 1969, as the second paragraph of it equated the Palestinian with the Iraqi citizen in terms of appointment, promotion, and retirement, but now, after canceling this decision, they are forbidden to retire. As well as on Iranian political refugees whose camps were closed arbitrarily and thus deported from Iraq.¹⁹

The cancellation of Revolutionary Command Council (dissolved) Resolution No. 202 caused a setback in the protection that Palestinian refugees receive, for example when Palestinian refugees were exposed to displacement in 2006-2007 and also after 2014, they were treated in the same way as dealing with Iraqis in terms of employment and study in universities. The new residence law for foreigners No. (76) of 2017 has exceeded these rights granted to them previously and deprived them of benefits such as the food ration and retirement, meaning that it negatively affected the humanitarian situation of the children of the Palestinian refugee, despite the fact that the prime minister has issued a clarification of the law, but it is not based on legal grounds. Also, Articles (2) and (3) of the Political Refugee Law define the Syrian refugee as displaced across borders.²⁰ Officials at the Ministry of Displacement and Migration stress that despite Turkish and Iranian refugees of Kurdish origin who have been in Iraq for 24 years, their

¹⁷ Sanaa Fadel Globe, UNHCR, round table meeting, Baghdad, 12/15/2018

¹⁸ Ibid, round table meeting, Baghdad, 15/12/2018

¹⁹ After 2003 and the collapse of Saddam Hussein's regime, Iranian refugees opposed to the Islamic Republic in Iran, who were present in Ashraf Camp in the Iraqi Diyala Governorate, were subjected to numerous harassment, were transferred to a camp near Baghdad airport, and were subjected to artillery shelling, and then they were transferred to Albania after the camp was closed.

²⁰ Muhammad Hantouk, Director of the Immigration Department at the Ministry of Displacement and Migration, round table meeting, Baghdad, 12/15/2018

main problem is still citizenship and obtaining official Iraqi documents while they have no problem in access to education.²¹

And the political conflict between the federal government in Baghdad and the Kurdistan Regional Government of Iraq in Erbil had a negative impact on the conditions of Syrian and Iranian refugees, as the federal government in Baghdad was unable to organize their data and provide them with the required documents pertaining to residence, their freedom of movement, and the guarantee of work. The presence of most of them was confined to the Kurdistan region of Iraq because they entered Iraq through the border outlets of the region and granted them privileges in housing, residence and work outside the framework of the mechanisms and instructions of the federal government, because this difference in the opportunities for protection was reflected on the reality of the refugees and the extent of their freedom of residence, movement and work throughout all of Iraq. In the same direction, the refugees in Iraq were directly affected by the aggravation of the economic crisis in the Kurdistan region of Iraq, as a result of political tension between the federal government and the Kurdistan Regional Government in Iraq. This economic crisis had repercussions on the overall needs of refugees, including an impact on access to health care, and they had to work more while waiting for the completion of their documents, in addition to the few schools that offer the curriculum in the Arabic language which were subject to closure due to the delay in paying teachers' salaries for months, as is the case with the rest of government employees.²²

The large deficit in the budget of Iraq and at the level of the Kurdistan region had negative repercussions on the conditions of refugees. Children who live outside the camps need psychological and social support services, as well as Iraqi children who are internally displaced. Education has also been affected by the economic and financial situation of the Kurdistan region, especially if we know that there have been periods when teachers who contracted with the Ministry of Education in the Kurdistan Regional Government did not receive their salaries for six months, and this led to a large number of teachers leaving for Europe, which caused a deterioration in the level of education for refugees, in addition to children with disabilities, they need qualified and specialized teachers. The lacking budget of the Kurdistan region of Iraq also affected the delivery of health services with the difficulty of obtaining medical treatment due to the closure of medical facilities and the lack of staff, with the scarcity of some medicines, and the risks of disease outbreaks. Refugees also suffered from scarcity of water, sanitation and electricity, and in the summer, these problems are magnified, and the issue of shelter and food is also a top priority and causing many obstacles for refugees.²³

These problems need solutions, including those related to the national internal level, including those related to the regional and international levels, as material and financial support for international governmental and non-governmental organizations must be increased, in addition to increasing the rate of resettlement of Syrian refugees.

²¹ Star Nowruz, previously cited

²² www.unhcr.org, February 2016

²³ www.unhcr.org, February 2016

3.5. Developments since 2011

Since Iraq has yet to legislate a refugee law - apart from political asylum, then there is no specific definition of protection in its national refugee law.

Iraq recognizes seeking and having asylum in the constitution, and this is confirmed by Article 21, paragraphs second and third of the Constitution of the Republic of Iraq for the year 2005, which have already been mentioned.

Most of the refugees to Iraq after 2011 do not consider Iraq as a country of final asylum but rather asylum to it, either as temporary or as a transit station for other countries, especially European countries, and the reason for this is that the refugees to it, they consider Iraq an insecure country, and it has many problems political and societal which have negative impacts on peace and security in this country.²⁴ The political issues were, and still are, a factor controlling the status of refugees. Iraq still calls the Syrian refugees and others as those displaced across borders instead of refugee or asylum-seeker. Years ago, formal communications began to be re-described, and since the issue of asylum is considered a sovereign issue for Iraq, therefore coordination between the MOMD and UNHCR was undertaken to prepare and manage a database related to refugees in Iraq, as the current reality reflects that Iraq is not a country of transit only rather, it is a country hosting refugees.²⁵

Despite the fact that Iraq has not joined the 1951 Refugee Convention and its 1967 Protocol, it is keen on its obligations to the standards of international law, especially agreements and declarations on human rights, so Iraq is keen on the legal protection of refugees by not sending them back to their countries forcibly and to adopt the principle of voluntary and without coercion.²⁶ While providing them with temporary shelter in their own camps or complexes, during the application process to obtain legal documents for asylum seekers, and after the asylum seeker obtains refugee status within the framework of the UNHCR procedures, the refugee has the right to: employment, education and access to public assistance. However, the process of access to the courts and to obtain identity documents, travel and housing constitute an obstacle to refugees in Iraq.²⁷

It can be said that the Iraqi authorities lack expertise in dealing with refugees and that the difficulties and problems faced by the Iraqi authorities regarding protection are their lack of willingness and ability to receive such large numbers, which alone in the Kurdistan region of Iraq reached nearly 250,000 Syrian refugees, so many of them lived in complexes in tents made from cloth.

The most prominent developments that occurred for the period 2011-2017 regarding the conditions of refugees and internally displaced persons can be summarized in the following:

- A large number of Syrian refugees entered Iraq, reaching 253,000, and nearly 240,000 residing in the Kurdistan region of Iraq.

²⁴ Interviews were conducted with Syrian refugees by the research team of the Respond Project in Iraq

²⁵ Star Nowruz, previously cited

²⁶ Law of the Ministry of Immigration and Displaced, 2009

²⁷ Refugee interviews at the miso level

- The Iraqi government allocated funds within its budget amounting to 50 billion Iraqi dinars, equivalent to 40 million dollars for refugees,²⁸ with the allocation of 400,000 Iraqi dinars for each Syrian refugee family in Anbar, equivalent to 330 dollars at the beginning of the crisis in 2011.²⁹
- Keeping the refugees and their camps away from the areas of tension; meaning that they are away from the areas entered by the terrorist group (ISIS).
- Canceling the privileges of Palestinian refugees and including their rights within the Law on Foreigners No. (76) of 2017.
- The deportation of Iranian political refugees from Camp Ashraf for political reasons.

²⁸ The 32nd meeting of the Iraqi Council of Ministers on 24/7/2012

²⁹ Meeting with a member of the Standing Committee for Refugees

4. Abiding by International Law

Iraq is one of the countries that signed the International Bill of Human Rights, and joined eight human rights agreements as mentioned above. Iraq is also committed to contractual and non-contractual mechanisms of the United Nations, including the submission of periodic reports on the human rights conditions to the Human Rights Council and is subject to the mechanisms of periodic reviews conducted by the relevant committees emanating from the international conventions on human rights ratified by Iraq, and also in the implementation of its obligations and mechanisms of the universal periodic review UPR including visits by special rapporteurs.

Iraq has also ratified most of the international instruments related to racial discrimination, including the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination 1965, and the International Convention for the Suppression and Punishment of the Crime of Apartheid (1971). It has also ratified the international instruments related to crimes against humanity, including the Convention to Prevent the Crime of Genocide and its punishment 1948. Iraq has joined most of the international instruments related to the right to physical and environmental integrity, including the Convention against Torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment

Among the important instruments that Iraq has also joined are those related to transnational organized crime, including the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime 2000, the protocol supplementing it to prevent, suppress and punish trafficking in persons, especially women and children 2000, and the other complementary protocol to combat the smuggling of migrants via the land and sea routes.

As for the instruments relating to the rights of women and children, Iraq ratified the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) 1979, the Convention on the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons and the Exploitation of Others 1949, and the Convention on the Rights of the Child 1989, and joined the Optional Protocol to it on the involvement of children in armed conflict 2000 and also the Optional Protocol to the Convention itself on the sale of children, child prostitution and pornography 2000.

Iraq has ratified a number of agreements relating to slavery, including the Supplementary Convention on the Abolition of Slavery, the Slave Trade, and Institutions and Practices Similar to Slavery, 1956, and the Protocol to Amend the Slavery Convention of 1926.

However, Iraq still has not joined the instruments related to international humanitarian law, especially the 1949 Geneva Conventions, related to armed conflicts to improve the conditions of the wounded and sick in the armed forces in fields and seas, to treat prisoners of war and protect civilians in times of war.³⁰ It has not yet joined the Migrant Workers Convention and their families.

³⁰ For more details, see Appendix No.

One of the indicators of Iraq's progress in its international obligations is it obtaining membership in the Human Rights Council in Geneva for the period (2017-2019) after the elections for the membership took place in October 2016.³¹

In its membership, Iraq pursues a method of non-selectivity in directing international protection, in addition to adopting the principle of objectivity, independence and good appreciation for the special rapporteurs who are selected and defining their mandates and tasks and not allowing the use of international protection of human rights to achieve political goals.³²

These expressions are mentioned in the official letter sent by the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Iraq to the United Nations on February 17, 2016, to request the nomination of Iraq formally for the first time as a member of the Human Rights Council. Obtaining membership in the Human Rights Council and the extent of its implementation of its relevant international obligations.

³¹ Muhammad Sahib Majeed, interconnectedness in human rights issues in the three councils: the Security Council, the Economic and Social Council and the Human Rights Council. Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Institute of Foreign Service, 2017, p.84-85

³² Previous source, p.84-85

5. Implementing International Protection on the National level

Although Iraq has mechanisms for protection in theory, however, the implementation and practice of these mechanisms have taken on a character consistent with the conditions of Iraq and its political, security, geographical and demographic conditions, especially with regard to the Kurdistan Region of Iraq. Many Syrian refugees and others chose Iraq for reasons related to its proximity and ease of access to it because it is a country adjacent to the countries from which these refugees came, as well as to avoid feeling alienated due to ethnic, racial, religious, linguistic and cultural interference, especially in neighboring countries.

Through fieldwork, the research team was able to identify points that reflected the extent of Iraq's ability to achieve appropriate protection, they are as follows:

5.1. Choosing Iraq as a country to take refuge in

Drawing from the interviews conducted with the Syrian refugees in Iraq, it can be argued that they preferred Iraq instead of going to Turkey or Lebanon, even though these countries are neighboring countries due to the ease of entry and obtaining residence and work, in addition to the lack of prosecution by the authorities or the presence of relatives or friends of them in the region. One interviewee says:

I took a decision to leave for Iraqi Kurdistan because it was safe after I found that it was more appropriate for me to arrive in Erbil because they would give a visa and residence easily, while Lebanon residence cost more and the difficulty of obtaining one (Irq-1 HFK-Micro-Syr-M-No.1)

Another refugee states that, "I did not come to take refuge outside Iraq because we are afraid of alienation," adding, "I sought refuge in Iraq because of the war in Syria, insecurity, instability in addition to the lack of work (12GAB-Micro-Syr-No.12Irq-)". In other words, in a more accurate sense, he came to Iraq for the sake of safety, stability and work.

5.2. The process of applying for asylum

Most of those who sought refuge in Iraq had prior information about the situation in Iraq and it was transmitted through refugees who preceded them or through their relatives who were in contact with them through well-known social networks or the phone. A refugee says "The information we took was from the people who immigrate, in addition to the information that my brother who preceded me coming to Iraqi Kurdistan five months ago" (Irq-14SHRO-Micro-Syr-F-No14). However, a number of refugees came to Iraq with no information about the situation, only that they joined the groups that were leaving collectively, and that the information they obtained about Iraq was from the Syrian refugees and that what was conveyed to them was not close to the truth, as the information was in many times exaggerated in terms of its positivity, as they gave them information that led to them being attracted to come to the Kurdistan Region of

Iraq, because the majority of this information comes from the Kurds, and the ethnic and racial similarities affected them. One interviewed refugee stressed that

I had no information about Iraq or any idea about the borders. I came with the rest of the people, we went through a rough time, had to walk and were very tired, and if there were no people coming to Iraq, we wouldn't have known the route because we don't know these roads, and many people were leaving Syria. I came with my two children. My daughter, who is with me now, was 3 months old, the child did not see her father who was killed in February and my daughter was born in August. The information we were obtaining from Syrians before us, and most of that information appeared to be contrary to the truth and exaggerated. The Syrians visiting Iraq and returning were transferring information to us, which turned out to be inaccurate. (Irq-15LYA-Micro-Syr-F-No.15)

A female interviewee asserts that

We had no information when we were in Syria about such a situation in Iraq, and what will happen to us after the asylum, where they tell us that things are good in Iraq and that you can find work with ease, and we girls can run a farm. But the reality is different from what was reported to us from Iraq, and while we were in Syria. (Irq- 21 PMF-Micro-Syr-F-No.21)

As for the expectations of refugees and their realistic experiences in the application and registration process, the largest number of Syrian refugees who were interviewed expressed their satisfaction with the way they were interviewed and the ease and short duration of obtaining the asylum application document and residence in the Kurdistan region of Iraq. One refugee stresses that he faced ease in registering indicating that the procedures were easy and within one hour the information was taken and we were granted a certificate of asylum from the United Nations and an identity with the right to work in Kurdistan ((Irq-4RLM-Micro- Syr-M-No.4). Another refugee confirms that

The procedures were easy and they are easier than expected" and added that "the investigators and the staff, their behavior was good, they took care of me as a woman, "she asserted." It took only two or three days to complete the procedure and I got the asylum application document, and I expected that it would take more. (Irq-18MYA- Micro-Syr-F-No.18)

While some refugees indicated that the procedures were difficult, they expected to obtain the documents in a shorter time than a week or two, but it took months. The interviewed refugee says

I expected that When I arrive in Iraq, I will present my papers easily for immigration. In a matter of one or two weeks, I will get asylum and residency, but it lasted for three months and I was given the document of asylum seekers, which is with me

and through it I got residency and moving around within Iraqi Kurdistan and also gives me the right to work. (Irq-17AFA-Micro-Syr-M-No.17). As for the nature of the procedures of registration, he stressed, "The procedures were difficult and long. (Irq-17AFA-Micro-Syr-M-No.17).

As for giving special consideration for vulnerable groups or gender differences, most of the refugees confirmed that the investigators dealt kindly with them, so the refugee himself stresses that "there was a special consideration given to the handicapped, women and the elderly in particular" while some indicated a little on the contrary. One refugee says

The process of applying was in the form of queues, and there was no distinction between a large or a small woman, they separated women from men, but there was no gender-based consideration, as they did not differentiate between an elder or a disabled person. They just relied on the role, just as there was no special consideration for women, children and pregnant women. (19EMS-Micro- Syr-M-No.19

Most of the refugees also expressed the lack of legal advice and that the process of guiding them to apply or register for the application for asylum or protection was through the camp management or through relatives, acquaintances or others who preceded them and guided them through the application. One refugee says "I did not receive support or legal advice, nor did I receive any material, moral or counseling support" (Irq-20RKA-Micro- Syr-M-No.20). Another refugee confirms

No one gave me legal advice. Rather, the one who provided support to me is a Syrian friend I know from the Levant, where I lived in the tent of his family who left the camp after they rented in Duhok, so the tent was furnished and had the remaining requirements. (Irq-24KJK-Micro-Syr-M-No.24)

Another refugee confirms that

No one provided me with legal assistance or advice or care for my children with regards to education" (Irq-18MYA-Micro-Syr-M-No.18). One refugee says "I did not obtain legal advice nor did I receive other assistance in education, language lessons, or training for children. (Irq-15LYA- Micro-Syr-M- No. 15)

It was also found that all the Syrian refugees went through the registration procedures because that requires them to obtain a document (proving that they are asylum-seeker) on the basis of which they obtain the right to residency, work and the right to housing, especially in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq. The refugee expresses

The asylum application document helps us in obtaining residency in Iraq and in the event that I do not get it, I do not obtain residency and I cannot work or move around because it is considered my identification, as it was found that few Syrian refugees

were aware of their rights and duties and know the difference between The rights of asylum seekers and the rights of refugees. (EMS-Micro-Syr-M-No. Irq-19)

One refugee says "I know the difference between alternative protection and the refugee's description" (Irq-21PFM-Micro-Syr-F-No.21). Another refugee says

My aim in seeking asylum is to ensure that I am not sent back to my country, when I am a refugee and has no authority over me other than the United Nations, it is written on my application that it is forbidden to forcibly return this person to his country, he is not a refugee but rather an asylum seeker, I am an educated person and I know my duties not to disturb security and not to harm the surroundings and customs and traditions and the importance of commitment to the rules of the society in which I live and other legal conditions. (3OMK-Micro-Syr-M-No.3 -Irq)

The same refugee added that "I do not know the refugee is different from the asylum seeker and I do not have any information about the refugee's rights and duties" (3OMK-Micro-Syr-M-No.3 -Irq)

One refugee stressed that "I don't know all my rights and duties as a refugee" (Irq-20RKA-Micro-Syr-M-No.20). Another refugee says "I know my rights as a refugee like security, safety and protection, and I don't know what my duties are" (Irq-11HFH-Micro-Syr-F-No.11).

5.3. Impressions from the viewpoint of refugees and asylum seekers regarding the procedures and the behavior of investigators

Most of the interviewees were Syrian refugees who said that the investigators who wrote and recorded their information were kind to them and there was attention to their needs and the needs of others in terms of gender (gender), the elderly or the sick, pregnant women, and others.

One says "there was consideration by UN staff for the sick and the elderly." Irq-6SHMH-Micro-Syr-M-No.6) Another refugee asserts "the procedures were in the camp and through the United Nations (UN), there was a special consideration in the registration, taking into account the elderly, children and women" (Iraq-13SAA-Micro-Syr-F-No.13). However, a few confirmed that the investigators did not observe the issue of attention to gender or the elderly and children but rather relied on who applied first at the time in terms of submission without taking into account other matters. According to one interviewee.

Applying was in the form of queues, there is no difference between someone young, old, or a woman, they separated women from men, but there was no gender consideration, as they did not differentiate between an elderly or a handicapped, they only depended on their place in line, as there was no special concern for women, children and pregnant women. (-Micro-Syr-M-No.19Irq- 19EMS).

Another refugee says during the registration "I conducted interviews and the investigators' behavior was vague. Everything was kept secret and they were uncomfortable while not paying attention to my personal needs". (Irq-3OMK-Micro-Syr-F-No.3).

As another affirms, "The protection system has changed and has become a special concern for marginalized groups, amendments have been made to laws, and safe havens have been provided." (Irq-1DGHY-Meso- F-No.1). It has also been found from interviews that all Syrian refugees who registered have been granted the status of "asylum seeker" because Iraq does not have a refugee law and does not grant refugee status except to political refugees according to the Political Refugees Law No. (51) of 1971, and that obtaining the (asylum seeker) document facilitates the process of obtaining residence and the right of movement, as well as obtaining the right to live outside the camps.

One refugee also states, "The asylum application document helps us in granting residency in Iraq and in the event, I do not get it, I do not obtain residency and I cannot work or move, it is a proof of identity." (Irq-19EMS-Micro-Syr-M-No.19). It says in the same context that most of the refugees who applied for registration got enough information in a language they understand and the most information was in an oral way because most of the applicants were Kurds or Kurdish speakers, and also that the investigators in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq used the same language for understanding. As for the duration of the procedures, most procedures took a few weeks or one to two months, with a few exceptions that lasted 6 months.

As one refugee says

After I entered the asylum procedures at the United Nations, I stayed five days at my relatives' house, they guided me to the asylum office in Erbil, filled out forms, submitted personal information, and presented information in a systematic way and received the asylum seeker document after two days." (MICRO-Syr-F-No.6Irq-6SHMH-).

A refugee also confirms that "We registered for asylum in Domiz camp, and the asylum form was completed by the United Nations, and we were given a certificate of the status of asylum seekers directly, but the residence took a month" (14SHRO-Micro-Syr-F-No.14Irq -).

As another refugee indicated "I expected that when I arrive in Iraq, I will present my papers easily for immigration. In a matter of one or two weeks, I will get asylum and residency, but it lasted for three months." (17AFA-Micro-Syr-M-No.17Irq-).

The interviews also showed that most of the Syrian refugees did not prefer to return to their country in the event they received a negative answer that did not satisfy them in obtaining the asylum application due to fear of the prevailing conditions and the instability in Syria, and the lack of job opportunities, as the refugee says "If a negative decision is issued against us, I cannot return to Syria because of fear and because my children were young when I came." (Irq-26FAR-Micro- Syr-F-No.26). One refugee who left Syria to escape joining the Syrian army

because his age was required for recruitment, said: "I think if my application was rejected I would have gone to any country except Syria", and he adds "I came for protection, not for the purpose of immigration." (Irq-20RKA-Micro-Syr-M-No.20) As another refugee says "I did not apply for asylum to a third country, nor did I submit anything for the future because I do not want to go to Europe, and I hope to return to my country if there are job opportunities "(Irq-6SHMH-Micro-Syr-M-No.6) while a refugee woman confirms ." If there is a negative decision regarding our asylum and the hope is lost, I will return to Syria. "(Irq-27RHH-Micro-Syr-F-No.27)

Likewise, some people were wanted for military service or for fear of being recruited into the armed Kurdish factions in northeastern Syria, as one said "and if the situation improves in Syria we will return" and he adds, "because of the recruitment by the compulsory groups (YPG), which are Kurdish forces loyal to the regime in Syria, immigrated to Kurdistan Iraq, "and also indicates" we did not plan to seek asylum or immigration, but the circumstances led us to that, which is the recruitment of my three brothers (Irq-14SHRO-Micro-Syr-M-No.14). A refugee who had eight daughters said that "we decided to take refuge in Iraq, especially after we heard rumors of recruitment of girls within the Kurdish organizations which happened after we moved to Iraq." (Irq-21PFM-Micro-Syr -M-No.21).

5.4. The role of non-State actors in regards to security

It was evident from fieldwork carried out by researchers that non-state actors had a limited role in specific matters especially in matters related to interference in the security issues, while they had a positive role in other issues, such as providing in-kind and logistical assistance. The team of researchers found that most Syrian refugees did not obtain legal advice from individuals or humanitarian or legal NGOs, as was previously mentioned, and that many of them even appointed private lawyers to follow up on their cases in exchange for cash payments to them. One Syrian refugee says, "I have completed residency through the attorney at the residency center on 100th Street, after the tourist visa I came in which I also obtained through the attorney has expired." (Irq-1HFK-Micro-Syr-M-No.1)

However, the team noted that organizations contracting with the United Nations in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq have contributed to the registration and organization of documents for Syrian refugees to give them asylum application document and provide the necessary services for registration, such as the Swedish Qandil Organization. One refugee says

I performed registration procedures in Qandil, which presented me with the application form, and that this organization is responsible for registering Syrian refugees, that the registration process took place after I contacted the organization and set an appointment for me after one month from the call, and after four months, my family joined the registration application, and the procedures were completed within four months. (Irq-3OMK-Micro-Syr-M-No.3)

As for the distribution of aid, most organizations focused on providing refugees with tents, water, food and construction material more than assistance in caring for children or providing lessons in education, language, etc. As confirmed by one interviewee (

We participate in leading three aspects: protection, coordination and management of camps, shelters, and basic relief materials, and we also participated in leading a cash working group that aims to provide people with cash to meet basic needs. (Irq-2KWV-Meso-F-NO.2)

In light of this, one interviewed refugee says "I received from the organizations (280) thousand dinars per child in school as an annual aid." (Irq-6SHMH-Micro-M-NO.6). The one refugee confirms "My brother helped us with housing, and the UN refugee agency provided us with tents." (Irq-12GAB-Micro-F-NO.12). The refugee says

I needed housing in the beginning and lived in an apartment in a Motel, and after two and a half months I found work that no organization helped with, No organization provided us with any help but after nine months we obtained from the Hammurabi Organization for Human Rights a relief quota that includes detergents, and then after that, the Qandil Organization gave us cash of some 465 thousand Iraqi dinars. (Irq-1HFK-Micro-Syr-M-No.1)

Elsewhere, the refugee says

An organization whose name I do not know came and built two rooms for us. They gave us 600 blocks, and we had 400 blocks, and they gave us a ton of cement. We also provided a ton and a half of sand, doors and windows. They did not give us everything. We complete what they couldn't. I am satisfied, praise be to God. (Irq-15LYA-Micro-F-NO.15)

As for the issue of providing a place to live, most Syrian refugees remain in the camps as the refugee says: "We lived two years in a tent, and then in the camp we built a two-room house, bathroom and kitchen at our expense, and we do not pay rent or water or electricity bills, but in the beginning we rented and paid money and I am now comfortable and happy." (Irq-11SHFH-Micro-Syr-F-NO.11). Another says: "My place of residence is the camp and I do not pay rent. I am neither happy nor comfortable in my residence, I prefer to leave this place if opportunities become available." (Irq-19EMS-Micro-Syr-M-NO.19)

As for those who preferred to live outside the camps, they depended on themselves, their relatives, or locals who helped them find a place to live, and most of them had to pay rent. One confirms: "I had a small amount of money, I was looking for a place to stay using housing offices, and I did not get support from organizations in this regard". (Irq-1HFK-Micro-Syr-M-No.1)

Refugees outside the camps rarely received assistance to support them to pay rent from organizations, families or other people. A refugee says: "No one helped me, I pay a rent of 200,000 Iraqi dinars per month, and I also pay the electricity fee and the costs of the generator which is paid separately." (Irq-21PFM-Micro-Syr-F-NO.21)

5.5. Family Unification

The issue of family reunion bears two directions, one of which is family reunion inside Iraq and the second is joining their relatives outside Iraq. With regard to the first direction, the research team noted that the Syrians who entered Iraq without the rest of their family members, the Iraqi law does not provide legal basis for family reunion with the rest of the family, as is the case in Europe. The rest of the family members joined their relatives in Iraq by entering Iraq in the same way that those who preceded them entered, after they were provided with the information required to enter Iraq, and some have resorted to joining their families by using various methods of crossing the border in a legal and illegal way.

One refugee recalls how she joined her husband with her children to Iraq, as she says: "My husband came 8 months before me to Iraqi Kurdistan," and she added: "I joined him through Al-Qamishli and with my three children crossing the border on foot" adding: "it was my husband who gave me the full information about the trip". (Irq-13SAA-Micro-Syr-F-No.13)

With regard to the reunification of Syrian refugees with relatives outside the country, it was found that a few refugees had relatives abroad who were eligible to work for them to get reunited, because family unification in Europe is assumed to obtain residency or citizenship and that most Syrians have relatives who have arrived in Europe within a period that does not allow them to go through family unification procedures.

One refugee says: "my son took refuge in Turkey by sneaking into the country, and from there one of the organizations helped him to go to Greece and from there to Germany three years ago, but he does not have German citizenship, so he cannot ask for family reunification." (Irq-26FAI-Micro-Syr-F-No.26)

Others have expressed that some who arrived in Europe were affected by individualism and did not care about their families or relatives living in the homeland. Also, a refugee says: "I have a brother in Belgium who lived there for three years, and I asked him for family unification. He said that it is difficult to do family unification, and he is married and has a family and children there." (Irq-22MAR-Micro-Syr-M-No.22)

One recalls "those who arrived at the diaspora do not think about us nor give any attention to the procedures of family reunification" as they affirm "despite having a sister and cousins and aunts in Britain, Norway, Belgium and Germany, and some of them got married in Iraq and went there, no one tried to reunite us because those who leave does not look behind them." (Irq-21PFM-Micro-Syr-F-No.21)

5.6. Detention, Deportation, Return, and Exposure

No Syrian refugees faced arrest or detention because of their arrival in Iraq, but a few have been subjected to deportation from the borders and failure to accept their entry because of the behavior of the security forces at the border towards different ethnic groups or because of the lack of knowledge of the Kurdish language, as one refugee states "I was not subjected to any deportation procedures or any problems and I was not subjected to detention." (Irq- 8ABA-

Micro- Syr-M-No.8) Also, one refugee asserts "there was no decision to deport or forced return, and I was not subjected to detention or arrest." (Irq-17AFA-Micro-Syr-M-No.17). Another says "no attempt has been made to deport me from Iraq, but my husband has been expelled from Saudi Arabia due to work issues" (Irq-2AFSH -Micro-Syr-F-No.2).

One refugee says "On the border people who had come more than once were sent back, meaning they came to Iraq and then returned to Syria and then tried to return to Iraq, these people were sent back. We did not face This problem because we came for the first time." (Irq-15LYA-Micro-Syr-F-No.15)

One refugee, who is of Kurdish origin, asserts, "On the borders, only Arabs were sent back, there was an Arab travelling with my but they did not allow him to enter. He did not speak Kurdish." (IRQ-20RKA-Maker-Sir-M-No. 20)

As for the return, Iraqi laws, especially the law of the Ministry of Immigration and Displaced, emphasize the importance of voluntary return and not resorting to coercion in forcing refugees to return, and the team did not find, through interviews, that orders for deportation of Syrian refugees from Iraq were issued.

6. Examples of few positive national practices

We see it is very important, if we want to refer to the Iraqi national contexts, in dealing with refugees and their protection, there are practices and positive elements in dealing with, although Iraq is not bound to the International Convention on Refugees and the agreements on stateless persons, but there is an important protection for them in its national laws. Iraq is one of the signatories of most of the major international agreements, and it has its national law on political refugees (51) of 1971, and despite its definition of a refugee it does not conform to a large extent with international standards³³, because the known international definition is completely different.

Iraq in terms of practical practice welcomed refugees in the past and continues to do so currently, as Palestinian refugees, for example, and not limited to them, are treated to the present day like Iraqi citizens, in terms of rights, in a more accurate sense, they have rights in terms of protection and safety, ownership, housing, education, movement, and getting documents and equality before the law and access to other basic rights up to the degree of equality with the rights of the Iraqi citizens, although the new law of residence in 2017, limited their rights, but the decisions and recommendations of the government is working to remove these restrictions.

One of the national practices that warrants reference is that Iraq, despite the absence of a special law on refugees, committed not to carry out forcible returns or deportation of refugees to their countries in an involuntary manner³⁴, especially since Iraq does not carry out deportation as long as the refugees' behavior and practices do not threaten the regime's stabilization and the security of the country.

The field work demonstrated by meeting the refugees themselves, and the organizations working in this field, that there is no deportation or forced return of refugees, and this records a positive success story in the nature of Iraq's treatment of the refugee situation.

³³ WP1 Report, refugee definition in Law 51 of 1971

³⁴ The principle of non-refoulement referred to in many of the international conventions on refugees or international human rights law has today become an international norm and commitment as it does not require the state to be a party to the 1951 convention.

7. Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) Situation

There is a similarity between the conditions of the Iraqi IDPs and the Syrian refugees, where security was lost and terrorist groups spread, which prompted millions of them to search for safe havens, that their suffering is the same and that they are two sides of the same coin. According to the statistics of the Iraqi Ministry of Immigration, a total of 5.5 million Iraqis was forced to leave from the northern and western provinces of the country (Nineveh, Kirkuk, Salah al-Din, Anbar, Diyala, the outskirts of Baghdad and parts of Babil Governorate) after ISIS took control of these areas in mid-2014.

The situation of the internally displaced Iraqis is complicated and their protection problems are complex. Many of them suffered from the brutality and savagery of ISIS who occupied their areas, and some of them suffered from the persecution of the security and armed forces on the pretext of their children's association with this terrorist organization and suspicions continued to circulate around them, which led to treatment of injustice and cruelty in addition to the harshness of nature; summer and winter caused much suffering. Also, some of them have been displaced from their regions more than once to different parts of Iraq. This was confirmed by the representative of the UNHCR in Iraq, Bruno Guido.

In mid-September 2018, there was a reverse return of thousands of IDPs from their areas of residence to the displacement camps again in different parts of Iraq, and that there are one million and nine hundred thousand IDPs, many of whom will not be able to return to their homes soon and aid must be provided to them.

The United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) has confirmed that more than 151,000 displaced Iraqi children have been exposed to harsh environmental conditions and risks to their lives due to the cold, low temperatures and floods in the winter and to the harsh hot weather in the summer period that characterizes the Iraqi regional environment, especially since most of the displaced families live below the poverty line in dilapidated housing that lacks heating or in camps that do not protect them from the cold ³⁵.

The suffering of the displaced in Iraq did not end even after the terrorist organization ISIS was eliminated in 2017 and expelled from the areas it occupied, despite the return of more than 3 million displaced people to their homes after the area was liberated. According to UN and other reports issued by committees in the Iraqi Parliament, there are approximately 1.8 million displaced Iraqis who have not returned to their homes for many reasons, including:

- Armed forces taking control of approximately 16 cities and towns and stopping their return under various pretexts and excuses, such as Jurf Al-Sakhr, Al-Owaisat, Yathrib, Baiji, Karagol, and other regions.

³⁵- Jasim AL- Shammari, Iraqi IDPs are two sides of the same coin. [https:// www.syria.tv](https://www.syria.tv)

- There is widespread destruction in some liberated areas, some of which have been reduced to ruins.
- There are tribal problems that await thousands of IDPs in the event of their return due to the affiliation of one of their members to ISIS, and what that means with regards to revenge and compensation.

Mr. Jasim Al-Attayah, Undersecretary of the Ministry of Displacement and Migration in Iraq, said to Anatolia Agency that there are about 500 thousand displaced people living in the camps spread throughout the country, in addition to about 700 thousand displaced people who are still in cities outside the camps³⁶

According to the data of the Joint Coordination Center (JCC), the displaced are distributed as follows:

- 40% displaced are Sunni Arabs
- 30% Yazidis
- 13% Kurds from the disputed territories
- 7% Christians
- 10% other minorities³⁷

The condition of the displaced Iraqis (who is left of them) can be described as between a hammer and an anvil, either living under miserable and harsh conditions in the camp, or returning to their homes in light of the loss of security and fears of the sleeping cells of ISIS in their areas and with destroyed infrastructure.

7.1. The Implementation of IDPs Protection.

Through the field work accomplished by the team of researchers, the team found that most of the internally displaced people were displaced from their areas of origin because of violence that occurred in their areas or because of armed conflicts, so they went to other areas that are safer for their lives and their children and that very few were displaced for economic and social reasons, and that number of internally displaced persons, exposed to more than a displacement due to the leakage of violence to the sanctuaries they had taken refuge in at first, which forced them to change their shelters more than once. For example, a female displaced says

After the incident of storming the Church of Sayedet Al-Najat in Baghdad at the end of October 2010, and my brother's kidnapping on the way between Baghdad and Sulaymaniyah, and his liberation by paying a ransom, the fear of staying in Baghdad increased, so I moved my job to Hamdaniya in Nineveh Plain that I chose because it was safe at the time and my family and relatives were there, but I was displaced again from Hamdaniya to Ankawa in Erbil, after ISIS invaded Hamdaniya in August 2014. (Irq-1REB-Micro-IDPs -F-No.1)

In the same context, as one displaced says,

³⁶ - [https:// www.aa.com.tr](https://www.aa.com.tr) 29/04/2019

³⁷ -<https://www.arabic.rt.com>. 20/08/2019

I was displaced from the city center of Mosul at the beginning of 2010 because of our exposure to threats by placing an envelope and in it a threatening message from Islamic extremist armed groups asking us to participate in Jihad, where they were facing the American forces, asking to pay a tribute of (\$4000) for being Christians, and they described the place of ransom delivery, we did not have the amount, but we collected it from relatives, it was delivered in the required place. (Irq- 2NYM-Micro-IDPs -M-No.1)

Another displaced person adds" I moved to Ankawa in Erbil because it is safer and closer to Mosul and for the presence of friends and relatives, after a while we returned to Mosul after a relative calm, but we were displaced again on 18/7/2014 after ISIS entered Mosul". (Irq- 2NYM-Micro-IDPs -M-No.1).

Another IDP from Ramadi says

We stayed in Ramadi until ISIS entered and left our area (Kabisa, a tribal rural area) due to the violence, we moved to Erbil in Diana, and stayed there for two months, after that my daughters, who were displaced from Mosul due to ISIS invasion, joined us, we were displaced again to Baghdad, and stayed at a school for 6 months in Baghdad, and then we moved to the camp for the displaced in Zayouna, Baghdad. (Irq- 6KHT-Micro-IDPs -M-No.6)

The research team noted that most of the IDPs interviewed obtained a legal protection by being registered as IDPs with the Ministry of Migration and Displaced which is the only official body that has the authority to grant Identification for IDPs and is also concerned with paying the financial benefits arising from each case of displacement, and in this context one displaced says "I have an IDP with my family received a displacement grant (one million) dinars from the Ministry of Migration and Displaced". (Irq- 7MHA-Micro-IDPs -M-No.7)

One displaced person says,

My legal status has been displaced after I attend the Ministry of Migration and Displaced I was given the identity of a displaced person in Sulaimaniyah, and as a result I have a valid residence, and for that I have the right to work." (Irq-12SFGH-Micro-IDPs-M-No.12). Another IDP says, "I am a registered IDP and I have an ID for IDPs and was granted one million dinars, some of us did not receive it because their names did not appear in the list of the Ministry. (Irq-13DEE-Micro-IDPs -M-No.13)

A displaced person confirms "My legal status is displaced and I have IDs, officially registered and there is no opposition to work." (Irq-15ASH-Micro-IDPs -M-No.15). In terms of support and humanitarian assistance to the displaced, it became clear through field work that the received assistance by the displaced was most concentrated for those who live in the camps, while those who lived outside the camps did not receive adequate support and assistance, whether living or other psychological and legal aid, and that humanitarian organizations. Local and international

civil society organizations, as well as families, played an important role in assisting the displaced, and religious institutions had a clear role in assisting the displaced, especially the churches in the Christian areas, the Husseiniyas, and the mosques in the areas of Moslem."

One female displaced says,

The situation was indescribable as families on the street, in unfinished homes and in gardens, the church and clerics had a positive role, families were embraced in churches and schools and fed the displaced collectively. The nuns also had a role, as well as donations from civil organizations and medical aid from Lebanese and Iraqi organizations, as well as from churches. (Irq-1REB-Micro-IDPs -F-No.1)

Another displaced person says,

The main institutions that helped us was Hammurabi Human Rights Organization and the Ministry of Migration and Displaced and we did not receive any assistance from international organizations knowing that civil organizations had an important role to help the displaced people, especially the poor ones, who do not have the financial means and who left their properties in their areas of origin. (Irq- 7MHA-Micro-IDPs -M-No.7)

Also, one displaced emphasizes,

Yes, we got in-kind assistance, food and health supplies only and we got oil from the local government, and we did not get any other help. The role of the organizations is a different role because they focused on the camps without IDPs, who are homeless and live in slums or home structures, it is incomplete because they needed more than that. (Irq- 23NSR-Micro-IDPs -M-No.23)

While another displaced person confirms,

We got help from local and international organizations such as ACN, Hammurabi Human Rights Organization, Assyrian Charitable Society, Salt and ACTED Organizations, but now all organizations aid has stopped after the liberation of Mosul, yes, the organizations helped the displaced to provide services they need and played a major role in the relief of the displaced, including the churches as well, while the government services were not integrated. (Irq- 20WNZ-Micro-IDPs -M-No.20)

One female displaced said: "we got help from UNHCR, as some of the caravans were given and fences, garbage containers, and fire extinguishers, as well as from Seven Sanabel Organization, a national organization that played a good role and provided assistance to the displaced". (Irq- 26TNA-Micro-IDPs -F-No.26)

Another displaced person confirms,

After we migrated to Latifiya and settled there, Hammurabi Human Rights Organization came and supported us with relief assistance. As for the local government in Latifiya, not help us, there are medical services that provide us and generally the services are weak, even though I have the right to obtain it from the state, we still had to buy medicines and we did not receive any legal aid. (Irq-8BSHH-Micro-IDPs -M-No.8)

8. Conclusion

Although Iraq has not joined the 1951 International Refugee Convention and its 1967 protocol, it has signed all international agreements, declarations, and human rights instruments regarding Human Rights. Therefore, asylum procedures related to refugee protection are based on Iraq's international obligations related to respect for human rights, while Iraq has no refugee law other than Political Refugees Law No. 76 of 1971 and the Ministry of Immigration and Displacement Law of 2009. With Iraq's keenness to fulfill its international obligations, in the field of human rights, however, the absence of a law for refugees in Iraq and its failure to join the International Refugee Convention generates a disruption in the daily practice of dealing with refugees and asylum seekers, and a lack of the international dimension for protection.

The fieldwork with the refugees revealed facts on the level of practices, procedures and challenges, and that the protection system needs reform, as most Syrian refugees in Iraq prefer to resettle in third countries if they have the opportunity and sufficient support, because of their fear of political and security instability in Iraq and the absence of a law that guarantees them the rights of refugees, especially since all of them who live in Iraqi Kurdistan are considered asylum seekers according to the documents granted to them by the UNHCR, but they are deemed refugees de facto and not according to the law, and that the UNHCR document is relied upon in granting residence in the region, on the basis of which it is possible to work and move around.

As for the rest of Iraq, there is no legal protection for Syrian refugees, and de facto refugees were dealt with without organizing data for them or issuing documents to them, until 9 April 2019, when the National Security Council decided that the legal description of the Syrian refugees should be displaced from the Syrian border region and they were welcomed for humanitarian reasons due to the reality imposed by the Syrian crisis.

Iraqi Ministry of Displacement and Migration continued registration process for Syrian Refugees in coordination with the UNHCR and in coordination with the Kurdistan Regional Government in Iraq, with the Ministry of Interior establishing a database to record biological information for them to coordinate with the Ministry of Interior in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq, provided that the Iraqi Ministry of Interior is granting temporary identification identities to them based on the Memorandum of Understanding between the Standing Committee for Refugees and the UNHCR.

The fieldwork also revealed the lack of desire among Syrian refugees to return to their country due to the continuing state of fear and security instability in Syria. In practice, there was a lack of adequate legal advice to refugees, a lack of translation services, the right to object to their status and decisions issued against them. In the same context, although there is respect for vulnerable groups and an interest in different social types, they need to legalize the provision of service to them, especially children, women, pregnant women, and the elderly.

In the absence of an integrated protection system, it was necessary to search for alternative types of protection and put in place mechanisms to promote the issue of family unification. In the framework of the work of the actors dealing with protection, besides the presence of more than one working body in the field of protection, whether at the governmental or non-governmental level or at the level of the work of local and international civil society organizations, there are many challenges facing these bodies represented by the weak level of coordination and division Work and cooperation between them, therefore requires the formation of working groups (Clusters) involving governmental and non-governmental bodies, and the development of mechanisms for cooperation and coordination between the federal government and the Kurdistan Regional Government, as well as coordination with local governments to ensure and strengthen mechanisms and ways of adequate protection.

9. Policy Recommendations

- The need for Iraq to join the International Refugee Convention of 1951 and its amended Protocol of 1967.
- The importance of Iraq speeding up the legislation on refugees, based on the importance of isolating the humanitarian side of their situation from the political side, especially since the new proposed refugee law mentioned above which covers a wide area of refugees human rights, is still in the corridors of Parliament, and there is still an opportunity to work on developing it.
- Create a comprehensive coordination framework between the agencies working in protection, whether between institutions of the federal government and those affiliated with the Kurdistan region of Iraq, or between local and international organizations, and forming joint working groups as previously mentioned.
- Working on unified legal frameworks related to managing refugee affairs and providing protection for them, with the unification of the authority concerned with migration and asylum, because currently the role of the Ministry of Immigration and Displaced Persons is limited to the humanitarian aspect, while the Permanent Committee for Refugees Affairs handles other technical matters, and this leads to disorganized efforts.

10. References

- [1] Iraq does not treat Syrians residing in its territory as refugees or asylum seekers, but it considers them guests according to the directives of the National Security Agents Council and the Iraqi Ministry of Immigration to prevent any opportunity to resettle them in Iraq or grant them Iraqi citizenship in the future
- [2] Horizon 2020, Respond, working Papers, Global Migration: Consequences and Responses, June 2018, p.365. www.respondmigration.com
- [3] Ibid, PP. 369
- [4] Look at table number 2
- [5] Look at table number 3
- [6] The Arab Charter for Human Rights, the most recent version, University of Minnesota, the Library of Human Rights www.hrlibrary.umn.edu, also see, the Arab Charter for Human Rights issued in the series of publications of the National Commission for Human Rights, Doha, Qatar Sunna, p. 11.
- [7] The Universal Declaration of Human Rights, United Nations brochure on the 70th anniversary of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, New York, 2017
- [8] There is no signature
- [9] A brochure in the series of publications of the National Commission for Human Rights, Qatar, Doha
- [10] Ashgabat Declaration, 2012 www.alanba.com.kw, published on 5/14/2012.
- [11] The Constitution of the Republic of Iraq, Fact Sheet / Iraqi Issue No. 2012, 28/12/2015.
- [12] Publication 12/23/2017, www.alsumaria.tv.
- [13] Horizon 2020, Respond Working Papers, Global Migration: Consequences and Responses, June 2018, p.377, www.respondmigration.com
- [14] Law of the Ministry of Immigration and Displaced, Article 2, 2009.
- [15] Star Nowruz, Director General of the Branches Department at the Ministry of Displacement and Migration, Roundtable Meeting, Baghdad, 12/15/2018
- [16] The proposed refugee law: It is the draft refugee law prepared by the relevant authorities in the Ministry of Immigration and Displaced and the Ministry of Interior represented by the Permanent Committee for Refugee Affairs in 2017, for organizing refugee rules and its provisions in Iraq to include all cases of humanitarian and political asylum due to persecution and threats based on race, religion or nationality or social affiliation, in line of the provisions of the Constitution of Iraq, international agreements and the enforcing laws with finding the relevant administrative structure, but this law has not been legislated until now. According to the letter of General Secretariat of the Council of Ministers, office of the Council of Ministers and Committees Affairs No. 041429 on December 28, 2017.
- [17] Sanaa Fadel Globe, UNHCR, round table meeting, Baghdad, 12/15/2018
- [18] ¹ Ibid, round table meeting, Baghdad, 15/12/2018
- [19] After 2003 and the collapse of Saddam Hussein's regime, Iranian refugees opposed to the Islamic Republic in Iran, who were present in Ashraf Camp in the Iraqi Diyala Governorate, were subjected to numerous harassment, were transferred to a camp near Baghdad airport, and were subjected to artillery shelling, and then they were transferred to Albania after the camp was closed
- [20] Muhammad Hantouk, Director of the Immigration Department at the Ministry of Displacement and Migration, round table meeting, Baghdad, 12/15/2018
- [21] Star Nowruz, previously cited

- [22] www.unhcr.org, February 2016
- [22] www.unhcr.org, February 2016
- [24] Interviews were conducted with Syrian refugees by the research team of the Respond Project in Iraq
- [25] Star Nowruz, previously cited
- [26] Law of the Ministry of Immigration and Displaced, 2009
- [27] Refugee interviews at the miso level
- [28] The 32nd meeting of the Iraqi Council of Ministers on 24/7/2012
- [29] Meeting with a member of the Standing Committee for Refugees
- [30] For more details, see Appendix No.
- [31] Muhammad Sahib Majeed, interconnectedness in human rights issues in the three councils: the Security Council, the Economic and Social Council and the Human Rights Council. Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Institute of Foreign Service, 2017, p.84-85
- [32] Previous source, p.84-85
- [33] WP1 Report, refugee definition in Law 51 of 1971
- [34] The principle of non-refoulement referred to in many of the international conventions on refugees or international human rights law has today become an international norm and commitment as it does not require the state to be a party to the 1951 convention
- [35] Jasim AL- Shammari, Iraqi IDPs are two sides of the same coin. [https:// www.syria.tv](https://www.syria.tv)
- [36] - [https:// www.aa.com.tr](https://www.aa.com.tr) 29/04/2019
- [37] -<https://www.arabic.rt.com>.20/08/2019

11. Appendix

Table.2 The actual interviews for Syrian refugees:

2014-2017 Arrival Date	2011-2014 Arrival Date	Ethnic Religious Minorities	Female No.	Male No.	Interviews #	Province
5	1	2	3	3	6	Baghdad
5	1	2	4	2	6	Erbil
6	1	3	3	4	7	Dohuk
3	1	2	2	2	4	Sulaimaniya
2	-	-	1	1	2	Najaf
2	-	-	1	1	2	Babel
2	-	-	1	1	2	Karbala
25	4	9	15	14	29	Total

The actual interviews for Syrian refugees:

Refugees by age group are divided into three categories according to the above table data

(18-38years), (9) male interview, (8) female interview.

(39-59 years), (5) male interview, (4) female interview.

(60 - More) (2) male interview, (1) female interview.

Table.3 The actual interviews for IDPs

2014-2017 Arrival Date	2011-2014 Arrival Date	Ethnic Religious Minorities	Female No.	Male No.	No. of Interviews	Province
5	1	2	3	3	6	Baghdad
5	1	2	4	2	6	Erbil
6	1	3	3	4	7	Dohuk
3	1	2	2	2	4	Sulaimaniya
2	-	-	1	1	2	Najaf
2	-	-	1	1	2	Babel
2	-	-	1	1	2	Karbala
25	4	9	15	14	29	Total

IDPs by age group are divided into three categories according to the above table data

(18-38 years), (5) male interview, (6) female interview.

(39 - 59 years), (6) male interview, (8) female interview.

(60 - More) (3) Male interview, (1) female interview.

Table.4. Other agreements on Human Rights and Iraq's position on them

International Bill of Human Rights				
	The name of the agreement	Date of entry into implementation	Iraqi position	Notes
1	United Nations Charter 1945			State party
2	The Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948			Formally adopted and issued by the General Assembly resolution 217 thousand (D - 3) of 10 K 1 1948
3	International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights 1966	1976/1/3	Ratification / Law No. 193 of year 1970	Iraq's reservation to does not signify it formal recognition of Israel
4	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966	1976/23/3	Ratification / Law No. 193 of 1970	Iraq's reservation to does not signify it of formal recognition . Israel

Instruments related to racial discrimination				
	The name of the agreement	Date of entry into implementation	Iraqi position	Notes
1	United Nations Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination 1963	Approved and published in public under General Assembly resolution (1904 (D-18) of 20 November 1963

2	International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination 1965	January 4th / 1969	Ratification / Law No. 135 of 28/8/1969	1-Reservation to Article 22 regarding approval of the mandatory jurisdiction of the International Court of Justice, and joining it does not imply official recognition of . Israel 2-Iraq joined the amendment of Article 8 of the Convention under Law 35 for the year 2001
3	The International Convention for the Suppression and Punishment of the Crime of racial segregation (Apartheid) 1973		Ratification / Law No. 92 of 1975	Reservation does not mean joining it formal recognition of Israel
4	International Convention against Apartheid in Sports		Ratification / Law No. 48 of 1989	And joining it does not mean formal recognition of Israel

Instruments related to crimes against humanity				
	The name of the agreement	Date of entry into implementation	Iraqi position	Notes
1	Statute of the International Court of Justice 1945			Not a party
2	Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the	k 2/1951 /12	Joined 9 / k 1/1948 and ratified in 1959	State party

	Crime of Genocide, 1948			
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Instruments related to the right to physical and environmental safety				
	The name of the agreement	Date of entry into implementation	Iraqi position	Notes
1	Declaration to protect all persons from torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment			
2	Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment	1987/6/26	Iraq 's accession by Law No. 30 of 2008	State Party
3	WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control 2003		Iraq ratified in accordance with Law No. 17 of 2007
4	Vienna Convention and Montreal Protocol for the Protection of the Ozone Layer 1985	And the Montreal protocol was implemented 1/January/1989 as amended at the eleventh meeting of the parties on 1999	Iraq has acceded according to Law No. 42 of 2007	
5	United Nations Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances 1988		Iraq has acceded according to Law No. 23 of 1996	
6	Convention on Biological Diversity		Iraq has acceded according to Law	

1992		No. 31 of 2008	
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year	The number	
2014	5	Law on the accession of the Republic of Iraq to an agreement banning or restricting the use of certain conventional weapons that may be considered excessively injurious or indiscriminate in effect and the protocols annexed thereto
2014	111	Law of Iraq joining the agreement on the physical protection of nuclear materials
2015	10	Law ratifying the amended agreement for Arab cooperation in the field of organizing and facilitating relief operations
2015	14	Law ratifying the agreement in the field of environmental protection between the government of the Republic of Iraq and the government of the State of Kuwait
2015	15	Law on the accession of the Republic of Iraq to the Protocol to Eliminate Illicit Trade in Tobacco Products
2015	45	Law on the accession of the Republic of Iraq to the Stockholm Convention on Organic Pollutants
2015	33	The Law of Ratification of the Republic of Iraq to Amend the Unified Agreement for the Investment of Arab Capitals for the year 1980 in the Arab Countries
2015	12	Law on the accession of the Republic of Iraq to the Agreement on the Promotional Framework for Occupational Safety and Health

2015	24	Law on the accession of the Republic of Iraq to the Agreement on the Promotion, Protection and Guarantee of Investments among the Member Countries of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation
2015	23	Law on the accession of the Republic of Iraq to the United Nations Convention on the Immunities of States and Their Property from Jurisdiction